

THEORETICAL BASIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ACTIVITIES OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Annotation. In the article, the importance of investment in the development of human capital in modern educational processes, the main priorities that determine the problems and activities of the development of preschool educational organizations in the internationalization of education, the organization of targeted activities in the development and effective introduction of innovative processes related to the industry, the content of competencies on, theoretical data on the methodological capabilities of the educator's competence in improving the quality and effectiveness of preschool education, based on educational needs and requirements, scientific and practical recommendations are presented.

Keywords: modern education, human capital, investment, internationalization, priority, “first step”, competence, educator competence, innovation, integration, consciousness, thinking, creativity.

In order to raise children from an early age to be well-rounded individuals, the issue of ensuring the effectiveness of education and upbringing based on the requirements of the times, achieving its level of global requirements, and through this, forming and improving the essence and content of education and upbringing, enriching the rules and laws of the preschool education system based on the rich experience of our people and searching for its new aspects, further improving the activities of preschool educational institutions, increasing the coverage of preschool children, and creating a modern system in all respects, while studying advanced foreign experience, was becoming urgent.

In recent years, our cooperation with UNESCO in the fields of education, science, cultural heritage, information and communication has been developing rapidly. In particular, with the support of this organization, a number of important programs and projects are being effectively implemented to preserve world cultural heritage sites in our country, restore cultural ties that existed on the ancient Great Silk Road, improve the quality of the education system and educate a harmonious generation, and develop the labor skills of young people in Uzbekistan. On this issue, the Head of State made his remarks in his speech at the opening ceremony of the "Second World Conference on the Education and Training of Young Children" held in Tashkent on November 15, 2022. In particular, “Based on the principle that “human dignity, its rights and interests are the highest value”, we have defined the creation of decent living conditions for the population of our country as a priority

direction of the policy of New Uzbekistan. In this regard, first of all, we attach special importance to paying attention and practical care to youth and children, raising them to be physically and spiritually perfect. By developing children from an early age and creating appropriate conditions for their education, we are creating a solid foundation for the full manifestation of their identity in the future. After all, there is no doubt that the investments made in the direction of such a noble goal will return many times over tomorrow. At the same time, we all know that the basis of a child's personality is formed precisely in preschool age, and the foundation for his intellectual and physical development is created during this period..."[1].

Foreign scientists have proven that investments in human capital that bring the greatest benefits in the future are those made at the initial stage of personality formation, that is, at the preschool stage.

It is worth noting that investments in preschool education for children from families with lower socio-economic status are more profitable than investments in children from well-off families. This is because preschool education not only contributes to the socialization of a child, but also creates the basis for the development of a person's intellectual abilities and prepares them for school. That is why the Concept for the Development of the Preschool Education System sets a target parameter of fully covering 6-year-old children with the school preparation system by the end of 2021.

The adoption of the "Concept for the Development of the Preschool Education System in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" has created a legal framework for implementing reforms in the field. Particular attention is paid to eliminating disparities between regions, cities and villages in the development of preschool education. In this regard, the state's policy of encouraging the attraction of private capital to the sector on the basis of public-private partnerships is also expanding opportunities.

In our country, preschool educational organizations carry out their activities based on the principles of creating opportunities for each child, developing their talents, passions and abilities, consistency, coherence and harmony in the education of children, cooperation with the family, education and upbringing, a personal approach aimed at developing the child's personality, democratic and secular characteristics, transparency and openness.

These tasks are provided for in the Resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 27, 2023 No. PQ-316 "On additional measures to further support public-private partnership in the field of preschool education", dated February 8, 2024 No. PQ-65 "On measures to further improve the activities of the customer service in the construction of facilities in the field of preschool and general secondary education", and in the Resolutions of the President of the Republic of

Uzbekistan dated May 26, 2023 No. PF-79 “On measures to effectively organize the activities of the Ministry of Preschool and School Education and organizations under its system”, dated February 23, 2024 No. PF-79 “On the State Program for the Implementation of the “Uzbekistan - 2030” Strategy in the “Year of Youth and Business Support” It is also specified in Decree No. 4236.

The "First Step" state program stipulates the use of collaborative approaches in preschool educational organizations, the development of children's creative abilities using various imitation games during classes, and the use of innovative methods in developing personal qualities in them.

In our opinion, preparing children for activities based on a collaborative approach in preparatory groups of preschool educational organizations is an interesting and developing form of work for them, as well as preparing them for joint mastery of more complex educational materials in the process of primary education. Scientific pedagogical analysis shows that preparing children for collaborative activities in preschool educational organizations provides for the following goals:

- preparing children for independent work in preschool educational organizations and primary grades;
- instilling in children elements of a culture of independent work in cooperation;
- developing children's creative abilities; forming in children an interest in certain areas and ideas about the importance of working together with members of society;
- instilling analytical thinking in children, etc.

As a result of organizing the process of preparing children for school within the framework of a collaborative pedagogical mindset, the following skills are formed in them:

- a) collaborative work on didactic materials;
- b) joint independent completion of tasks;
- c) analysis of the acquired information;
- d) development of creative abilities, etc. [5].

As a result, children feel comfortable in preschool educational organizations, get used to looking at themselves from the outside, and begin to critically evaluate their own behavior.

As a result, they are able to identify their own shortcomings, begin to listen to each other's opinions, pay attention to the opinions of their peers, and acquire the

skills to reckon with their opinions. Teaching children to collaborative activities in the process of preschool education has the following possibilities:

-if children successfully establish cooperation with their peers in the group, they effectively perform cognitive operations during the training process;

-when children successfully establish communication with their peers in the group, their vocabulary increases rapidly;

-as a result of children's social interaction in the process of preschool education, a team of children who have mastered certain knowledge is formed, who are ready to assimilate new information in the process of communication and perform cognitive operations together.

During the period of preparation for school, the following types of educational cooperation can be implemented:

-implementation of educational cooperation between educators and students;

-organization of educational cooperation of children with their peers in the group;

-implementation of self-knowledge of the child and interaction with the educational materials being studied during the preparation process, etc.

Based on the analysis of foreign experience, the following recommendations can be made for the further development of the preschool education system in Uzbekistan:

Respect for the rights of the child in Germany, regular improvement of the qualifications of educators and high qualification requirements for them, increasing the responsibility of parents and the good organization of joint work with them, effective use of experiences in the field of "Mothers' School" and training of pedagogical personnel;

Implementation of best practices in the United States of America regarding the mandatory nature of school preparatory groups for all in the preschool education system and the assessment and certification of children's knowledge;

Implementation of the positive experiences of Greek preschool educational institutions in providing parents with children's menus and educational programs in advance, and the provision of transport to bring them to the institution and take them home;

Effective use of aspects such as daily information exchange between parents and educators, differentiated payment of fees for children, their socialization, and adaptation to community life, which are typical of the preschool education system in Japan;

It is advisable to apply the experiences of South Korean preschool educational institutions in developing children, establishing cooperation between parents and educators, in-depth teaching of a foreign language in preschool educational

institutions, comprehensive harmonious development of children, teaching them technical safety rules, and familiarizing them with nature to preschool educational institutions in our country[4].

Today, the tasks of the preschool educational process are based on the fact that it is aimed at developing the child's basic skills, such as cognitive skills, aesthetic taste, communicative competence, moral skills, and physical activity.

The state curriculum "First Step" states that children should master the competencies of their own "I" and the individual characteristics of others, tolerance, and the ability to enter into interpersonal relationships in society in the area of competencies in the field of "social and emotional development". The Concept for the Development of the Preschool Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 sets as a priority the creation of conditions for the comprehensive intellectual development of preschool children, their mental and physical health, and, in particular, the improvement of the methodological system for instilling gender tolerance skills in children based on modern education and upbringing.

Today, one of the most important areas for the further development of preschool education is the widespread introduction of modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies into the educational process. Recently, comprehensive measures have been taken in this area to introduce an information system for managing preschool education, as well as systems for providing public services for enrolling children in state preschool educational institutions through State Service Centers or the Unified Portal of Interactive State Services of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan is ensuring the comprehensive development of students by introducing modern advanced forms of teaching, new pedagogical and information technologies into the educational process. At the same time, the current state of preschool education requires the further development of telecommunications infrastructure, ensuring the connection of preschool educational institutions to the broadband Internet network, and the development of effective organizational and pedagogical forms and methods for raising a spiritually mature younger generation.

Innovative development of preschool educational organizations in globalization educational processes is considered important for today, requiring a high level of competence and professional development from specialists and educators in this field. Based on modern educational needs and requirements, priority research is being conducted to improve the quality and effectiveness of preschool education, improve and apply the methodology for the formation of competencies of students and modern didactic tools, form the consciousness, thinking, and spirituality of preschool children, develop new theoretical concepts based on conceptual design to expand the philosophical, psychological, and

pedagogical capabilities of comprehensively active, creative, spiritual and moral upbringing of preschool children, and focus educational methodological and didactic support on high-quality educational goals.

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